

SULFUR IN LUNAR APATITE REVEALS LOCALIZED VOLATILE PROCESSES: IMPLICATIONS FOR METAL MOBILITY

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Introduction: Understanding the mobility of sulfur in the lunar interior is fundamental for reconstructing volatile behaviour, redox evolution, and potential redistribution of metals during magmatic differentiation. The lunar mantle is generally considered isotopically homogeneous in sulfur, an assumption based on the limited $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ variability observed in mare basalts and troilite grains [1, 2, 3]. Despite apatite's capacity to host sulfur and record late-stage volatile processes, its sulfur chemistry in lunar samples has not yet been systematically investigated, leaving a major gap in our understanding of sulfur behaviour in the lunar interior. Apatite is one of the few volatile-bearing phases capable of incorporating sulfur in both reduced and oxidized forms [4], and variations in sulfur content and oxidation state in apatite can reflect conditions that influence the solubility, transport, and redistribution of chalcophile and siderophile metals in evolving lunar magmas.

To investigate whether localized volatile-driven processes relevant to metal mobilization may be detectable in lunar samples, we conducted simultaneous NanoSIMS analyses of S and Cl isotopes in apatite, complemented by S isotope analyses of troilite, across a broad range of lunar lithologies from multiple Apollo landing sites.

Results and Discussion: The investigated samples encompass both pristine igneous rocks and lithologies showing evidence of late-stage degassing, vapour-phase activity, and development of vesicles and vugs, textural features indicative of volatile processes.

Troilite grains across mare basalts from different Apollo landing sites preserve homogenous, mantle-like $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ signatures. In contrast, apatite exhibits a wider range of S and Cl abundances and isotopic compositions than coexisting sulfides. While many apatite grains preserve mantle-like $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, others exhibit pronounced deviations toward both heavier and lighter signatures, indicating localized isotopic fractionation at the scale of individual melt pockets during late-stage crystallization. Apatite from different textural positions (apatite enclosed in pyroxene vs. apatite within mesostasis domains) shows comparable isotopic variability, indicating that these signatures reflect magmatic conditions at apatite crystallization rather than post-magmatic processes. Positive $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ - $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ and S-Cl abundance correlations in apatite from Apollo 12 and 14 basalts indicate closed-system

crystallization and incompatible-element enrichment during melt evolution. Conversely, some basalts from Apollo 15 show deviations from mantle-like $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values, from strongly enriched to heavily depleted $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values, along with significant decoupling from Cl.

Localised redox and $f\text{O}_2$ gradients likely develop during late-stage melt evolution as volatile species exsolve and interact with residual, chemically evolving melts. Mesostasis domains, where apatite commonly occurs in the investigated rocks, act as small-scale reservoirs that capture these transient conditions, preserving the effects of volatile enrichment and depletion but also variable degrees of vapour-melt interaction and degassing. At the outcrop scale, further investigation may clarify whether textures such as vesicles, vugs, and interstitial voids provide macroscopic evidence for open-system behaviour, potentially marking localized pathways for vapour-melt exchange, melt depletion, and diffusion. Within such domains, localized sulfur volatilization, oxidation, and isotopic fractionation can occur under low-pressure and near-surface conditions [2]. Magmatic sulfur degassing is a redox-sensitive process and well documented in terrestrial (hydrous) systems, both in experiments and in natural samples; recent studies also show that sulfur degassing alone can impart measurable oxidation to magmas, independently of other oxidizing inputs [5]. Similar micro-scale processes may operate in late-stage lunar magmas as pressure decreases, where localized sulfur loss could contribute to subtle but significant oxidation. Because chlorine is expected to remain largely unaffected under relatively anhydrous conditions, low pressure, and transient, moderately oxidizing conditions [6], sulfur is preferentially modified, producing large $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ excursions without corresponding changes in Cl. These open-system processes generate fine-scale chemical and isotopic heterogeneities that are invisible in bulk-rock measurements and in-situ troilite grains, but are preserved in apatite.

Conclusion and further studies: These isotopic fractionations imply dynamic changes in S and Cl speciation that regulate ligand availability and metal-ligand complex formation, key controls on metal solubility and mobility in magmatic systems. Variations in S valence state, the activity of Cl-bearing complexes, and transient oxidizing conditions within localized domains collectively influence the

potential for metals to partition into fluid/gas, melt, or solid phases. Our data therefore reveal the specific chemical conditions and spatial gradients that could enable metal mobilization in the lunar interior where metals are present, even in an overall volatile-poor system. These microscale records provide new constraints on volatile-driven redox and speciation dynamics in lunar magmas and highlight the late-stage processes such as degassing, vapor-melt interaction, vesiculation, and micro-environmental oxidation that may concentrate or redistribute metals. Together, these findings refine models of localized metal enrichment and volatile evolution on the Moon and underscore the importance of accessory minerals like apatite as archives of small-scale but geochemically significant processes.

Further studies will extend this work by directly examining how these volatile-driven micro-environments regulate the behaviour of metal-bearing phases.

References: [1] Wing B. A. & Farquhar J. (2015). *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 170, 266-280; [2] Gargano A. et al. (2022) *American Mineralogist* 107, 11; [3] Li, Y. et al. (2025). *Nat Commun* 16, 5780 ; [4] Brounce, M. et al. (2019) *Am. Mineral.* 104, 307–312; [5] Farsang and Zajacz (2025), *Nat Geoscience* 18, 98-104; [6] Tattitch et al. (2021) *Nat Comm* 12, 1774.